

SELF-CONFIDENCE IN ENGLISH AND PERFORMANCE IN PURPOSEIVE COMMUNICATION OF FIRST YEAR ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS

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Self-Confidence in English and Performance in Purposive Communication of First Year English Major Students

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Abstract

This study measured the level of self-confidence in English of 36 first-year English majors of Kabankalan Catholic College who were officially enrolled for the Academic Year 2022- 2023. The participants' self-confidence in English was classified into five macro skills namely reading, writing, listening, speaking, and viewing skills. Their self-confidence in the five skills was correlated to their performance in Purposive Communication course. Descriptive-correlational design was used to determine the association between the two variables. An adopted and compiled standardized questionnaires from different sources were administered. Mean, standard deviation, t-test, and Pearson correlation coefficient were utilized for data analyses. The results revealed that males garnered higher mean results in the level of self confidence in English in terms of listening, reading, writing, and speaking skills while females excelled in viewing skills. This finding implies that males are more confident in English compared to females. In terms of school of origin when taken as a whole, viewing skills got the highest mean while writing skills got the lowest mean for both private and public schools which implies that viewing skill is dominant due to digitalization and wide impact of media. Significant differences also vary in the five macro skills. A significant relationship was found between the students' self-confidence in English in terms of reading skills and their performance in Purposive Communication. Thus, the study suggests that language programs may be implemented to help enhance the students' English skills so they can fully excel in their academics and in the use of English language.

Keywords: *self-confidence, English, performance, purposive communication, English major*

Introduction

The English language is considered as an important means of communication all over the world. Szeder (2021) stated that having a good command in English helps us to have more opportunities in life especially when it comes to our careers. In the Philippines, the English language is considered the country's second language which is generally used in the field of education as medium of instruction in different institutions. However, not all Filipino students are confident enough with their English proficiency and skills. Students' self-confidence in speaking the English language varies from high or low, which eventually affects their performances in different courses that require excellent communication skills.

As a matter of fact, a student's high self-confidence and communication skills generate a significant impact on almost every aspect of their lives in terms of managing daily activities, dealing with life's challenges, and interacting with others (Shore, 2010, as cited in Berdan et al., 2020). Additionally, there may be a noticeable impact on their academic performance. It goes to show that the lack of self-confidence and poor communication skills can have a detrimental impact on the student's motivation to learn, capacity to concentrate, and willingness to take risks.

On that note, this study aimed to measure the self-confidence in English of the first-year English majors and how it correlates to their performance in the Purposive Communication course. We chose to study the level of self- confidence because it is necessary for a language teacher to be equipped with enough knowledge and self-confidence to teach and use the said language. English major students have the need to immerse themselves in studying the universal language in preparation for them to be experts in the field of language teaching. Thus, this study was conducted.

Research Questions

This study intended to determine the level of self-confidence in English of First Year English Major Students of Kabankalan Catholic College and how it correlated to their performance in Purposive Communication course for the First Semester of the Academic Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of self-confidence in English of the participants when grouped according to sex and school of origin and when taken as a whole in terms of the following skills:
 - 1.1. listening skills;
 - 1.2. speaking skills;
 - 1.3. reading skills;
 - 1.4. writing skills; and
 - 1.5. viewing skills?
2. What is the level of performance in the Purposive Communication course of the participants?
3. Is there a significant difference on the self-confidence in English in terms of the aforementioned skills of the participants when

they are grouped according to profile?

4. Is there a significant relationship between self-confidence in English and performance in the Purposive Communication course of the participants?

Literature Review

Self Confidence

One of the success factors for students learning or speaking English is self-confidence. Self-confidence is the capacity for persuasion and self-awareness in carrying out tasks and selecting a successful strategy. It entails confidence in their judgments or ideas, as well as trust in coping with a situation that is getting more difficult. High self-confidence, learners will speak or communicate in any circumstance, whether inside or outside of the classroom (Yundayani et al., 2019).

Many students experience poor self-confidence, especially when learning English. According to Akbari and Sahibzada (2020), a predominant cause of the problems ailing the educational system at the moment is a deficiency of self-assurance. They lack self-confidence due to a lack of preparation, a lack of belief in themselves, a lack of vocabulary and incompetence, and a lack of practice speaking in front of an audience (Nadiah et al., 2019).

Akbari and Sahibzada (2020) stated the level of self-confidence was found to be a significant factor in the learning process for students, including sharing opinions, developing relationships with peers and teachers, setting goals, managing anxiety, and developing interest in lessons to learn more effectively.

Omidullah Akbari et al. (2020) examined the effects of students' self-confidence on education. Although research has shown that self-esteem and self-efficacy affect performance engagement, neither the relative contributions of these two components nor the combined effect of these two factors have been established. Additionally, there is a dearth of studies on the controlling factors of student involvement.

Purposive Communication

The only language and communication course in the new general education curriculum, Purposive Communication (PC), offers learners numerous opportunities to improve their skills. Gairan (2022) stated that Purposive Communication is a three-unit course that develops students' communicative competence and enhances their cultural and intercultural awareness through multimodal tasks that provide them opportunities for communicating effectively and appropriately to a multicultural audience in a local or global context. It equips students with tools for critical evaluation of a variety of texts and focuses on the power of language and the impact of images to emphasize the importance of conveying messages responsibly.

Five Macro Skills Listening skills

Listening skills are important for learning because they allow students to gain new insights and knowledge as well as communicate effectively with others (Nuraini, 2019). Nonetheless, one cause of the unsatisfactory communicative process in the listening skill is pronunciation (Enciso et al., 2019, as cited in Orlando, 2020).

By increasing listening skills, English language learners will have better ability in English communication because listening skills help students recognize several aspects of speaking skills, such as multifarious accents, intonations, and pronunciations of different language users (Andujar & Hussein, 2019). In daily life, listening is an everyday activity that plays an important role in receiving information (Nushi & Orouji, 2020). Briefly, listening is a skill that encompasses comprehension and thinking skills (Kapanadze, 2019).

Speaking Skills

Speaking is a talent that is productive and has many different elements. Making the proper sounds, selecting the appropriate words, and understanding structures are only a portion of speaking (Rao, 2019). Conveying meaning also had to follow the context of the conversation and be easy to understand since speaking was the ability of EFL students to release their voices and express their thoughts (Lingga et al., 2020).

Speaking from personal experience focuses on communicating reality. Although people express their feelings in a variety of ways, all experiences share several features in common (Yin, 2019; Chen et al., 2020).

Reading Skills

Reading also makes a person more innovative and creative (Fitria, 2019). A study stated that when students comprehend what they are reading, the more they read, the better they understand each word's meaning in English. Reading is an essential mode for successful learning in a school setting, and competent reading goes beyond decoding as it also includes text comprehension (Zaccoletti et al., 2020). Hall et al. (2019) found that reading was an activity to catch, understand, know, or get literal pattern information. Reading comprehension contributes to nature understanding, linguistic development, and skill, i.e., vocabulary knowledge, grammatical skill, and morphological knowledge (Cervetti et al., 2019).

Writing Skills

According to Khazrouni (2019), writing skills are a thinking tool for the other three language skills and language components, such as vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar.

Viewing Skills

Shehada and Amer (2019) stated that there are many types of effective visual aids. A visual aid can be defined as a video. A video can give us access to real-life situations when learning a second language.

Khafidhoh (2019) suggested that even if young EFL pupils may not understand every word in spoken English when participating in different activities, visual aids, such as body language, pictures, or items, benefit their ability to understand, process, and acquire English vocabulary (Chamba & Gavilanes, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive correlational design to determine the self-confidence of the first-year English majors of Kabankalan Catholic College through a survey questionnaire and its correlation to their performance in the subject of Purposive Communication.

According to Lemboye (2019), the descriptive correlational design was relevant when describing research variables and investigating their natural relationships or associations. Hence, this design was also considered applicable since the study aimed to determine the significant relationship between the student's self-confidence and performance in the Purposive Communication course.

Participants

The participants of the study were the first-year English major students of Kabankalan Catholic who were enrolled for the academic year 2022-2023. The total population of First-Year English-major students consists of 36 students.

Instruments

The study adopted standardized questionnaires from various reliable and trusted sources. With this, we did not have to question its validity and reliability since it was already taken from published studies and authorized language websites and were divided into five macro skills namely reading, writing, viewing, listening, and speaking skills.

Procedure

In gathering the data of the study, we sent a letter to the Dean of the College of Education, Kabankalan Catholic College, College Department, seeking permission regarding the conduct of the study among first-year English major students, gaining access to the master list, and conducting a study wherein they will answer a survey questionnaire that we will provide. Before the actual testing, we also sent a letter to the adviser or subject teacher of the first-year English major students, for they will take part in the study as participants. We also conducted a face-to-face orientation, stated and clarified the purpose of the study, gave clear instructions on how to deal with and answer the research instrument, and assured them of the confidentiality of the data to be collected from the study. However, there were challenges, such as the other participants being absent during the orientation and others having already stopped their schooling. The expected number of participants can't be achieved.

We gave the questionnaires to the participants after receiving approval from the Dean and consent from the Adviser or Subject Teacher. Subsequently, we collected the test questionnaires.

After conducting the study, we compiled and encoded the results obtained from the research instrument. The collected data was sent to the statistician for statistical treatment and analysis of the results and findings.

Data Analysis

To analyze and generate the results and findings of the study, the study utilized the mean, standard deviation, t-test, and Pearson correlation coefficient.

Ethical Considerations

The following ethical considerations were observed in the conduct of this study:

In the collection process and handling of data and information, we assured the participants. Furthermore, the participants were guided on how to deal with the 25-item research questionnaire with self-confidence, which secured their anonymity.

On the storage and safekeeping of files and data gathered, academic records and survey results of the participants were kept locked in the storage cabinet, to which authorized personnel were only allowed direct access.

On disposal of information, all the data gathered, such as the performance results and survey results, were disposed of by shredding or

burning the documents based on the availability of disposing materials in three years after the completion of the research study.

Results and Discussion

Level of Self-Confidence in English

On the level of self-confidence in English of the participants when grouped according to sex, the findings revealed that male participants had the highest mean score in the four macro skills namely listening skills (3.89), speaking skills (4.03), reading skills (3.86), and writing skills (3.71). At the onset, female participants had the highest mean score in viewing skills (4.00). This implies that male participants are more confident than female participants. In this instance, this explains that, due to the same exposure to learning modalities, male participants are more flexible in acquiring a lot of macro skills in learning a language.

When the variable sex is taken as a whole, viewing skills had the highest mean score of 3.96 among the five macro skills while writing skills got the lowest mean score of 3.43. This implies that majority of the students are being engaged with the utilization of media. They usually use it for their studies through interactive and informative videos that provide them with knowledge that they need for their assignments, examinations, and other academic requirements. It became more evident when the education system was affected by the pandemic and students have to deal with distance learning modality where independent learning is expected from them. As supported by Katona et. al (2023), the education sector has been greatly impacted by the digitalization era's progress, as evidenced by the numerous advancements in learning media that may be utilized to boost students' enthusiasm to learn. However, the participants showed that writing skills are the most tedious and challenging among the other skills. According to Elbashir (2023), there are various causes that affect the writing skills of the students and it includes a lack of practice, a lack of time, a lack of motivation, feedback from the instructor, and the nature of the writing process.

On the level of self-confidence in English of the participants when grouped according to school origin, private schools got the highest mean scores in reading skills (3.84), writing skills (3.66), and listening skills (3.63). On the other hand, public schools had a few points to go beyond those of private schools in viewing skills (3.96) and speaking skills (3.88). The results showed a little difference between the level of self- confidence of the students who came from private and public schools. This implies that it is due to the two years of distance learning caused by the pandemic where the students were exposed to the same modes of learning. However, it cannot conceal the fact that private schools are more consistent on harnessing the English skills of the students.

Based on the findings of Dixit (2019), private schools have fared better than public ones in terms of performance. Additionally, Parajuli and Thapa (2017), as cited in Millendez (2023), claimed that private institutions probably offer a quality of instruction from the teachers and the availability of facilities are also intact. Research findings proved that the academic performance of private schools was better than that of their government counterparts. This was due to the accessible resources and services that a private institution could offer, such as sufficient materials in libraries and science laboratories, using modern technologies, and actively involving the students' discussions.

When taken as a whole, viewing skills got the highest mean score of 3.96, while writing skills got the lowest mean score of 3.43. This implies that viewing skill is still dominant due to digitalization and wide impact of media.

Level of Performance in Purposive Communication

On the level of performance in purposive communication of the participants when grouped according to sex, the results revealed that female participants got the highest level of performance in Purposive Communication with a mean score of 3.62, while male participants got a mean score of 3.29. This implies that female participants had ample time and focus to study. They were more serious and dedicated compared to male. When taken as a whole, the level of performance of the participants was high.

On the level of performance in Purposive Communication of the participants when grouped according to school of origin, the data presented a mean score of 3.55 for public school which was quite close to the 3.56 mean score of private school. As a whole, with a mean score of 3.56, both schools had a high level of performance in the Purposive Communication subject. This result explained that both schools' level of performance was quite similar since, during the pandemic, the learning access of the students happened at their homes through the distance-blended learning modality. Both schools used the same learning procedure to continue the learning, so the learners had the same exposure to the learning materials which were aligned to the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Also, during the pandemic, since not all parents of the participants are teachers that can guide them, there was no other option for them but to pursue self-study.

The close results were explained by Martin (2022), as cited in Williams (2022), who stated that private schools were statistically smaller in class and school size than public schools, generating a smaller teacher-to-student ratio and creating a more tight-knit environment. In this environment, students were more likely to be passionate and express themselves.

Significant Differences in the Self- Confidence in English

Based on the results, there was a significant difference on the reading skills ($t(34) = .68, p = .007$) and viewing skills ($t(34) = -1.32, p = .043$), of male and female participants respectively. On the other hand, the findings presented no significant difference on both sexes

in writing ($t = 1.44, p = .07$), listening ($t = 2.88, p = .64$), and speaking skills ($t = .95, p = .195$). Thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected since two macro skills were significant between the male and female participants.

In the above result, there was a significant difference between the reading and viewing skills due to the exposure to learning materials brought about by modular and blended learning. It showed that participants differed in their level of self-confidence when grouped according to sex. Male participants got the highest level of self-confidence among the three macro skills, namely, reading skills, writing skills, and listening skills. Female participants, on the other hand, were more confident in their viewing and speaking skills. In learning, boys were often found to be quiet and observant, whereas girls were creative but talkative.

When grouped according to school of origin data presented a significant difference between the reading skills of students coming from private and public schools ($t(34) = 1.047, p = .039$), while there was no significant difference found in the writing ($t(34) = 2.219, p = .936$), viewing ($t(34) = -0.071, p = .657$), listening ($t(34) = 1.421, p = .179$), and speaking ($t(34) = -0.242, p = .697$) skills of students from between private and public schools, respectively.

It goes to show that students from a private school have the highest level of reading skills. It simply means, perhaps, that the students from private schools performed better and had the possibility of a wider range of comprehension. This result was closely related to the findings of Dixit (2019), which stated that private schools have fared better than public ones in terms of performance. In addition, there are differences in academic achievement between public and private schools. She argued that private school students have produced better performances than those from public schools.

However, the null hypothesis was not rejected since the four remaining macro skills—writing, viewing, listening, and speaking—found that there was no significant difference in performance in purposeful communication among first-year English major students when they were grouped according to school of origin. Students coming from both private and public schools performed better in English based on the aforementioned macro skills.

Significant Relationship between Self-Confidence in English and Performance in Purposive Communication

After a keen analysis, the findings revealed a significant association between the self-confidence in English and the performance in Purposive Communication of the participants in lieu with their reading skills with a p-value of 0.43. Therefore, it is evident that self-confidence in English indeed plays a vital role to the performance of the students on their communication subjects in terms of reading since it will enable them to be precise on their expression, tone, diction, and pronunciation especially when they conduct oral reading activities. Ballane (2019), who stated that self-confidence was crucial to learning, development, and achieving academic success, corroborated the findings of this study. It was discovered that self-confidence predicted academic achievement. Higher academic success is correlated with higher self-confidence.

In contrast, the results also yielded a non-significant association between the self-confidence in English and performance in Purposive Communication of the participants in terms of their writing skills with a p-value of .275, viewing skills with a p-value of .836, listening skills with a p-value of .739, and speaking skills with a p-value of .808. The data implies that the writing, viewing, listening, and speaking skills of the participants do not have an association with their test performance in Purposive Communication because taking a test does not necessarily correspond to these mentioned skills compared to reading where the students really need to comprehensively read between the lines in order to come up with the correct answer. Carnegie Mellon University (2019) further added that students' lack of motivation for learning was caused by their lack of confidence in their ability to progress, as well as the fact that other priorities take up more of their time and attention. Bouilheres et al. (2020) also added that self-efficacy, self-esteem, and self-compassion were the three key characteristics that might alter a person's level of self-confidence. Self-confidence was associated with success, educational achievement, and personal reconciliation. Filippello et al. (2019) state that a person's level of involvement in school can be predicted by their self-esteem.

Conclusions

The study concludes that learning a language has a lot of factors to consider that may alter its development, including self-confidence, gender, and context of learning. These may have positive and negative impacts on learning the second language. Based on the findings, we have found out that we cannot stereotype all women that they are more confident than men, especially in the five macro skills of learning. With the constant changes in time, men were recognized for their academic excellence compared to women. Reciprocally, women tend to outperform men nowadays due to their intensive focus on learning. In measuring the level of self-confidence in the English language, this study twisted our traditional perception that women are always confident in using the language. As shown in this study, male participants were found to be more confident in the four out of five macro skills, namely listening skills, speaking skills, reading skills, and writing skills, compared to female participants who were confident in viewing skills only. This explains that we cannot always define people by their level of self-confidence through gender. It always ends with the line that each individual has a unique identity and capacity, not just for their cognitive and psychomotor abilities but also for their affective factors of learning.

On the other hand, the school of origin also plays a vital role in learning. The learning environment and the modalities affect the language acquisition of the learners. In this study, we found that students from private schools perform better than those from public schools. Most students who have a high level of self-confidence are from private schools. Taking into consideration that private schools

offer a lot of learning modalities that would help the learners acquire the lessons easily, the presence of books, modules, technologies, and other instructional materials was found effective for the students from private schools since the result of this study revealed a high level of self-confidence in their reading skills.

Both private and public schools produce confident students in English since, in the past years of the pandemic, they have the same mode of learning, which is modular or blended learning. The effect of distance learning really showcased that nothing can replace the effectiveness of traditional face-to-face learning. However, private schools had shown some remarkable benefits that were closely related to the result of this study. Firstly, students from private schools were confident in their listening skills for the common reason of being disciplined by school policies. They tend to listen, as they need to understand and respect what their teacher instructs them to do. Secondly, students were confident in writing since the workbooks or modular activities allowed them to develop their critical thinking in writing. Moreover, the teachers of private schools were required to make their own types of test questions to assess the students' learning. Thirdly, students were confident in reading since they provided enough reading materials for each student, which they could practice during their individual learning. Furthermore, private schools have a smaller number of students. In that case, they can accommodate each of their students well through face-to-face or virtual learning. It is possible in this school context since private schools have a lot of educational tools that can help students because of their affordability. Lastly, a high confidence in reading skills could highly impact one's performance in Purposive Communication course.

References

- Akbari, O., & Sahibzada, J. (2020). Students' Self-Confidence and Its Impacts on Their Learning Process. *American International Journal of Social Science Research*, 5(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.46281/aijssr.v5i1.462>
- Andújar, A., & Hussein, S. A. (2019). Mobile-mediated communication and students' listening skills: a case study. *International Journal of Mobile Learning and Organisation*, 13(3), 309. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmlo.2019.100432>
- Ballane, G. (2019). Understanding of Self-Confidence in High School Students. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=7676&context=dissertations>
- Berdan, J., Garfil, T. E., and Garucho, N. (2020). The Level of Self-confidence and Communication skills of None DHSBNHS in Grade 11 Stem of Doña Hortencia Salas Benedicto National High School S.Y. 2019-2020. <https://www.studocu.com/ph/document/lacarlotacity-college/english-proficiency-test-reviewer/research-final-nagid/35319518>
- Bouilheres, F., Le, LTVH., McDonald, S., Nkhoma, C., Montera, L.J. (2020). Defining Student Learning Experience through Blended Learning. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-020-10100-y>
- Carnegie Mellon University. (n.d.). Foster Belonging & Self-Confidence - Eberly Center - Carnegie Mellon University. <https://www.cmu.edu/teaching/designteach/teach/classroomclimate/fosterbelonging.html>
- Cervetti, G. N., & Hiebert, E. H. (2019). Knowledge at the Center of English Language Arts Instruction. *The Reading Teacher*, 72(4), 499–507. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26801637>
- Chamba, M., Reinoso, M., & Rengifo, E. (n.d.). Authentic materials to foster writing skills in college EFL learners. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1216686>
- Chen, C. (2020b). The Application of Affective Filter Hypothesis Theory in English Grammar Teaching. *Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 4(6). <https://doi.org/10.26689/jcer.v4i6.1294>
- Correlational Analysis of the Relationship among Mastery Experience, Self-Efficacy, and Project Success - ProQuest. (n.d.-c). <https://www.proquest.com/openview/1c2e97e7c09d1ce400fa52a14f98bd33/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Dixit, P. (2019). Analysis of CSR Impact on Private Sector Secondary School: A Study in North and South Delhi (India). https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3513118
- ELbashir, B. (2023, September 27). Writing Skills Problems: Causes and Solutions - International Journal of English Language Teaching (IJELT). *International Journal of English Language Teaching (IJELT)*. <https://ejournals.org/ijelt/vol11-issue-5-2023/writing-skills-problems-causes-and-solutions/>
- Filippello, P., Buzzai, C., Costa, S., & Sorrenti, L. (2019). School Refusal and Absenteeism: Perception of Teacher Behaviors, Psychological Basic Needs, and Academic Achievement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01471>
- Fitria, W. (2019). Reading Interest and Reading Comprehension: A Correlational study. *Jurnal Educative*, 4(1), 95. <https://doi.org/10.30983/educative.v4i1.1333>
- Gaoiran, M. (2022, April 15). Purposive Communication. <https://oursoul.su.edu.ph/OER/index.php/ourSOUL-%20OER/article/view/105>
- Hall, J. P., Van Horne, A. O., & Farmer, T. A. (2019). Individual differences in verb bias sensitivity in children and adults with

- developmental language disorder. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2019.00402>
- Hanafi, H., & Nuraini, K. (2019). Teacher Communication Pattern in English Learning process as Foreign language in Senior High School. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Community Development (ICCD 2019)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/iccd-19.2019.55>
- Khafidhoh, K. (2019). Material Development for Peer-Assisted Learning Program (PALP) in higher education. *ideas.repec.org*. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/ibn/assjnl/v15y2019i1p32.html>
- Lingga, L. M., Simanjuntak, R. M., & Sembiring, Y. B. (2020). STUDENTS' STRATEGIES IN LEARNING SPEAKING SKILLS AT SMP NASRANI 3 MEDAN. *Journal of Languages and Language Teaching*, 8(1), 91. <https://doi.org/10.33394/jollt.v8i1.2238>
- Millendez, Q. (2023). Academic performance and learning anxiety in English of elementary pupils in time of COVID-19 pandemic. <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=21995>
- Nadiah, N., Arina., & Ikhrom (2019). The Students' Self-Confidence in Public Speaking. <http://www.elitejournal.org/index.php/ELITE/issue/view/1>
- Nushi, M., & Shahhosseini, K. (2020). On the Efficacy of a Communicative Framework in Teaching English Phonological Features Absent in Persian to Iranian EFL Learners. *DOAJ (DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals)*. <https://doi.org/10.22054/ilt.2020.51623.486>
- Orlando, M. E. (n.d.). Teaching pronunciation to adult speakers of Spanish in Business English Lessons: Two aspects to consider. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1311045>
- Shehada, S. M., & Amer, O. D. (n.d.). Perceptions of Palestinian Students towards Using Audio Visual Aids in the English Language Classroom at the University Level. <https://journals.qou.edu/index.php/jropenres/article/view/1853>
- Szeder, S. (2021). Why is it important to speak English? <https://www.universitylanguageschool.com/student-blog-why-is-it-important-to-speak-english/>
- Use of Visual Learning Media to Increase Student Learning Motivation. (n.d.). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372227206_Use_of_Visual_Learning_Media_to_Increase_Student_Learning_Motivation
- Williams J. L. (2022). Understanding Education Variances in Our World: An Analysis of Private and Public Education on Graduation on Graduates' Educates' Effects in Society. https://scholarcommons.sc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1582&context=senior_theses
- Writing Skills Problems: Causes and Solutions. (n.d.). <https://ejournals.org/ijelt/wp-content/uploads/sites/57/2023/09/Writing-Skills-Problems.pdf>
- Yundayani, A. (2019). Investigating the Effect of Canva on Students' Writing Skills. *Yundayani | English Review: Journal of English Education*. <https://doi.org/10.25134/erjee.v7i2.1800>
- Zaccolletti, S., Camacho, A., Correia, N., Aguiar, C., Masón, L., Alves, R. A., & Daniel, J. R. (2020). Parents' Perceptions of student academic motivation during the COVID-19 Lockdown: A Cross-Country Comparison. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.592670>

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